

Thermal Comfort along with Physio-Mechanical Behavior of Lurex Integrated Knitted Fabric as Sweater

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Abstract

This project investigates the influence of Lurex yarn on the thermal comfortness of knitted single jersey fabric along with physio-mechanical behavior for the use of sweater. Lurex yarn is characterized by its metallic appearance and unique properties, often used to add shimmer and sparkle to textiles. The research assesses the impact of integrating Lurex yarn on key parameters such as mechanical strength and dimensional stability of single jersey structures. Experimental techniques, including fabric thermal comfortness by FTT, bursting strength, abrasion, and pilling tests, were employed. The single jersey samples were prepared using Lurex yarn combined with cotton and PVT fibers. The findings demonstrate that the incorporation of Lurex yarn has a significant impact on S/J fabric's performance. Specifically, the addition of Lurex yarn effectively reduced pilling and increased the mechanical strength of the fabric significantly. For instance, bursting strength improved from a mean of 689.4 kPa (Cotton S/J) to 901.3 kPa (Cotton S/J with Lurex). As per analysis (full feeder) Lurex integrated PVT sample is best for winter wear, breathable and comfortable wear is found to be cotton fabric at the same time Lurex reduces the comfortness with the increase of the amount of yarn. So it is clear that Lurex is mainly preferable when a knitwear is designed for aesthetic purpose rather than comfortness. The results contribute to a deeper understanding of the physio-mechanical behavior of these fabrics, supporting potential applications in fashion and performance textiles.

Keywords: *Metalic yarn, single jersey, thermal property, physio-mechanical property.*

Introduction

The insights considering evolution of Lurex yarn and its importance across various industries was examined from studies. The Lurex yarn has been known for its glamour, style, creativity, shimmer and versatility, making it popular across various industries. Its goal is to get fabric with better luster and visual effects, showing reflective properties of silver-colored Lurex yarn in tight fabrics with various yarns like viscose, polyester, wool, and Lurex (Jerhov, 2021). Lurex yarn is a metallic or metallic-coated yarn that adds a shiny, sparkling, or metallic appearance to the fabric. This type of yarn is often used as a decorative element in textiles to make a glamorous effect (Hasan, 2022). Metallic yarns are made from synthetic film coated with metallic particles or aluminum foil, offering vibrant colors like red, blue, green, gold, and silver. They add reflective, decorative patterns to woven, braided, and knitted fabrics and trims, often blended with wool, nylon, cotton, or synthetics for unique effects and they require specialized dry cleaning and low-temperature ironing for care (Texpedia, 2016). Several reputable options for metallic

Article History:

Received: 01.02.2026

Revised: 08.02.2026

Accepted: 26.02.2026

Published: 03.03.2026

Citation: Akter, S., Akter, S., Chowdhury, M., Dola, D.R., Tasnim, L., & Jannat, H. (2026). Thermal Comfort along with Physio-Mechanical Behavior of Lurex Integrated Knitted Fabric as Sweater. *European Journal of Science and Modern Technologies*, 2(2), 72-84. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejsmt.2026.2\(2\).06](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejsmt.2026.2(2).06)

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yarn are available in the market today such as Kreinik, DMC, Rainbow Gallery, Sulky, Anchor, Biella (Hasan, 2022; Davis, 2021). Lurex yarn stands for its metallic sheen, made from metallic or metallized polyester. It's highly sought-after in fashion and textiles for creating striking garments, accessories, and home décor (Desai, 2014). It comes in various colors, thicknesses, and finishes, allowing designers to experiment with textures and effects in both traditional and contemporary designs (Cook, 1959). It is lightweight, remarkably durable, and suitable for creating comfortable yet elegant clothing. Fibers like cotton, silk, or wool, polyester, nylon, or acrylic are used. As metallic component aluminum, polyester-coated aluminum, and polyester-coated nylon are used. These materials are typically available in the form of thin strips, sheets, or films (Yang, 1991). The metallic component is combined with the base fiber to create Lurex yarn. This can be done using various methods which are, plating which involves wrapping the metallic component around the base fiber. The metallic material is wound spirally around the fiber at regular intervals. Another one is laminating method, where the metallic material is applied to the surface of the base fiber using an adhesive or bonding process (Kashid, 2019). There is twist, in which threads or fibers are twisted together with the base fiber during the spinning process to make a textured and more variegated look. It can be used in various textile crafts, including knitting, crocheting, weaving, and embroidery to add a metallic element to various projects. The yarn comes in different colors, thicknesses, and textures. Lurex yarn is often used in special occasions as evening wear, costumes, and festive decorations as metallic fibers do not tarnish. Those using polyester films are the strongest, and can be stretched to a considerable extent (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, 1998). It may cause skin sensitivity due to its metallic fibers, making it less suitable for direct skin contact in clothing and accessories. Crafting with Lurex yarn may require adjustments like using larger needles or hooks and handling it gently to avoid stretching or breaking. It also offers less stretch and a different feel compared to regular chenille yarns (Richard, 2021). Lurex yarn's adaptability has enabled its use in varieties of applications such as; Fashion Industry, Textile and Home Décor, Craft and DIY and designers working with Ardil also uses it for many applications. Its incorporation inhome decor has allowed for the creation of visually appealing and functional products (Johnson, 2020). It is known for its metallic sheen, is evolving to meet modern demands, particularly in sustainability, functionality, and innovation. **Sustainable Lurex yarn** is crafted using eco-friendly processes, including recycled materials and non-toxic coatings, and focuses on reducing environmental impact through energy-efficient production methods. These advancements make it ideal for eco-conscious fashion and green-certified home decor. **Blended yarns**, where Lurex is blended with fibers like cotton, wool, or nylon, enhance durability, softness, and versatility, making the yarn suitable for various applications, from shimmering garments to luxurious upholstery. Meanwhile, **smart textiles** incorporate Lurex for its conductive properties, blending aesthetic appeal with cutting-edge technology. This enables applications in wearable, health-monitoring fabrics, and responsive textiles that integrate sensors, LEDs, or circuits, bridging the gap between fashion and functionality. Together, these developments highlight the adaptability and modern relevance of Lurex yarn in sustainable and innovative textiles. "NASA-Tricot" refers to a lightweight, radar-reflective knitted fabric developed by NASA. It enhances traditional tricot fabric with properties suited for aerospace and space exploration, including thermal insulation and electromagnetic interference shielding (Matthews, 1971). Metallic fibers have ruled the ramp in both men's and women's attire. Adding Lurex yarn to Mesta improved its strength and appearance. Mesta Lurex demonstrated better tenacity and breaking extension than Mesta and jute when their tensile properties were compared (Agarwal, 2019).

The inclusion of metal yarn is central to developing conductive textile structures, which are utilized in numerous applications across fields such as industry, the military, medicine, communication, and automation, with research focusing specifically on their potential for conductivity and electromagnetic shielding effectiveness (EMSE). The density of the metal yarn incorporated into the knitted fabric directly influences resulting properties, including conductivity, pilling, abrasion, and EMSE, and generally, increasing the amount of stainless steel in the unit area per fabric will increase EMSE values (Eroğlu,

2019; Sancak et al., 2018). In studies comparing single jersey knitted fabrics made with double folded yarn (A1) against those with single folded yarn (B1), the double folded yarn structure (A1) generally resulted in improved physical and shielding characteristics: the A1 fabric exhibited better pilling resistance due to the high cohesion force of the fabric and better abrasion resistance compared to the B1 fabric, a result linked to the A1 yarn's higher twist level. Furthermore, the A1 fabric showed better EMSE values, which is thought to be a consequence of the high density of the wire structure in the double layer fabric. However, when considering electrical current flow, the single folded yarn fabric (B1) demonstrated higher conductivity results along with lower surface resistivity and lower volume resistivity, indicating that its low resistance more easily permits the movement of electric current, whereas the use of double folded yarn (A1) conversely increased both surface and volume resistivity (Eroğlu, 2019).

Other studies similarly confirm or complement these findings-

- Çeken et al. (2012) studied plain knitted fabrics with stainless steel conductive yarns and measured EMSE in the range 750 MHz to 3000 MHz, reporting that stitch density and yarn insertion pattern affected shielding performance under different polarization conditions.
- Sancak et al. (2018) investigated interlock knitted fabrics with core-spun conductive yarns incorporating stainless steel, copper, and silver-coated wires, and found that increasing the course density and thickness of conductive wire correspondingly increased EMSE (and decreased surface resistivity).
- Bedeloğlu et al. (2013) observed that fabrics knitted with two-folded yarns often exhibited better EMSE values than those with single yarns, and that thinner conductive wires could lead to higher shielding effectiveness.
- Rajendrakumar et al. (2012) examined metallic yarn construction parameters (e.g. plating technique, wire diameter, yarn linear density) and showed their influence on shielding effectiveness and surface resistivity in knitted fabrics.

Materials and Methodology

Materials

Lurex yarn, PVT and cotton yarn used to create various types of knitted fabrics where the Lurex yarn has count 1/75 nm and the composition is 100 % Lurex, the PVT has count 29 Ne and the composition is 30% rayon 53% recycle polyester 17%, nylon (trade name Tactel) and cotton yarn has count 30 Ne and the composition is 100 % cotton. Those yarn collect from local market of Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Knitting

Flatbed knitting machine is used for the fabric production. The machine specification is HQPDS 16, it is a pattern design software of new generation machine. It has an automatic programming function of generating lower computer controlling data (Zhejiang Hengqiang Technology Co., Ltd., 2010). From the yarns different fabric sample produce for further experiments. Those sample have four variety for plain single jersey fabric. It is one of the simplest and most common knit fabric structures. All plain single jersey sample use same yarn feeder (left 1,5) knitting where efficiency 99% (high Speed:16 minutes. medium Speed:21 minutes, low Speed: 29 minutes) and equal courses (950).

Experimental Work

Fabric Comfortness by FTT

To evaluate the thermal properties of the plain single jersey fabric samples are measured simultaneously using fabric touch tester (FTT) (M293, SDL Atlas, which useful for the findings and comparisons of thickness and bending measurements of the sample by four modules and measures various touch-related fabric physical properties indices at both sides and in both directions (“Analysis and comparison of thickness and bending measurements...,” 2017).) The method follows ISO 5084:1996 where for FTT, first sample cuts in an L shape (31x31 cm) and the fabric set into the machine and collects the data (ISO, 1996). The FTT system automatically measured key thermal parameters, including thermal contact conductance (TCC), thermal conductivity related parameter (TCR), and maximum heat flux (Qmax).

Pilling Property

This pilling test performed by placing the specimen on a pilling tester and using a gentle friction method to be pilled a certain number of times and then evaluating it. This test is performed with MAG Auto Pill 4Bx Serial No: 8939184014 machine which is use for pilling test for any kind of any fabric. The process begins with prepare the fabric sample in square piece as specify in the testing standard such as ISO 12945-1:2020. Typically, the size is around 12.5cm×12.5cm. After that, set the Martindale Pilling Tester and install the appropriate abrasive material on the lower test table or base and then placing the knit fabric sample on the upper test table or specimen holder. Determining the test parameters such as the number of test cycles and the load or pressure applied during testing is necessary. The upper table moves in a circular motion, causing the fabric to rub against the abrasive material on the lower table. Once the specified number of test cycles is completed or stop the machine (ISO, 2020).

Abrasion Resistance

Fabric samples are placed flat and rubbed in a figure eight like motion using a cloth of worsted wool as the abradant. This test is performed with Martindale Abrasion & Pilling Tester (James Heal) and ISO 12947-2:2016 (ISO, 2016). The main function is that its helps to determine the abrasion & pilling. The test starts with sample cutting (diameter: 38mm) in circular sample of the knit fabric and adjust it with a piece of abrasive material same size as the fabric sample according to the standard. Then setting the test parameters according to industry standards and requirements which commonly used 10,000, 20,000 or more cycles. In the final stage, place the fabric sample on top of the abrasive material on the Martindale Abrasion Tester. Start the machine, which will rub the fabric against the abrasive surface in a control manner. For final result examine the fabric sample for any signs of wear, damage, pilling, or holes. No.of cycles were recorded cycles which took to visible changes. The higher the number, the better the fabric's abrasion resistance (James Heal, 2016).

Bursting Strength

The bursting strength test is a common quality control test use to determine the strength and resistance of materials to rupture or bursting under pressure. For this test conditioned atmosphere is mandatory. starting the test according to ISO 13938-2 with sample cutting according to specimen size and shape and make sure the edges are clean and free of defects (ISO, 2019). Then place the prepared specimen into the clamping ring or diaphragm fixture and ensure its secure position. Lastly Record the pressure at which the specimen bursts which is the bursting strength of the material. The bursting strength is typically measured in units like pounds per square inch(psi) or kilopascals (kPa). The pressure range is normally kept at 1000, kg/cm² (James Heal, 2016).

Shrinkage and Spirality

Shrinkage test is typically performed to determine the shrinkage properties of a material, which can be important in various industries such as manufacturing, construction, and materials science. Firstly, shaped the sample dimensions into standardized specimens and record the initial dimensions for each specimen. For shrinkage Processing the sample will be 50×50 cm & benchmark should be 35×35 cm as per ISO standard 5077:2007 (ISO, 2007). Afterward using washing machine, the shrinkage value can be evaluated through this equation: $\text{Shrinkage \%} = (\text{Before wash length} - \text{After wash length} / \text{Before wash length}) \times 100$.

According to ISO 16322-2 spirality procedure conduct via cutting the sample from the knit fabric make sure the sample should be large enough to perform the test accurately (ISO, 2021). Then mark two parallel lines to the fabric's edges before wash, and measure it after wash. For calculating the value, the formula is:

$$\text{Spirality} = (\text{Average spiral distance} / \text{Total distance}) \times 100 \text{ (G. G. F. Journals, 2010).}$$

Result and Discussion

Thermal Comfortness

The work demonstrate that cotton and PVT fiber percentage shows a significant change in thermal properties. The compression (CW) and compression recovery (CRR) is higher in cotton sample compare to PVT sample due to natural fiber crimp and air entrapment. On the other, PVT fabrics exhibit lower CW and higher compression recovery (CRR) but when Lurex is added compression recovery and elasticity deceases due to metallic property of yarn. This suggesting that cotton have better feels softness and fluffiness under pressure, while PVT recovers shape faster after deformation but due to Lurex the softness reduces (Hes, 2008).

Table 1. The Findings of The FTT Fabric Indices for Lurex Integratted Knitted Fabric

Index			Fabric types					
			S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
Compression	T	mm	1.17	1.22	1.19	1.07	1.13	1.12
	CW	gf*mm	1136.51	3007.42	1228.97	1293.25	3046.32	1253.23
	CRR		0.75	0.50	0.59	0.71	0.50	0.61
	CAR	gf/(cm ² *mm)	253.04	90.00	168.90	235.67	85.43	176.00
	RAR		521.26	207.26	338.73	512.64	192.64	316.49
Flux	TCC	W*mm/(m ² *C)	50.25	68.01	55.71	55.65	76.26	67.11
	TCR		50.85	65.91	57.31	56.22	77.96	69.31
	Qmax	W/(m ²)	526.20	354.70	404.32	569.73	377.97	462.40
Primary Sensory	Smoothness		0.47	0.34	0.40	0.58	0.44	0.52
	Softness		0.85	0.92	0.89	0.90	1.12	0.98
	Warmness		0.80	0.61	0.68	0.94	0.74	0.83

Figure 1. Fabric's Indices for Smoothness

Figure 2. The Findings of The FTT Fabric Indices for Warmness

In thermal flux behavior PVT fabrics results greater TCC, TCR, and Qmax values (Le, et al., 1995). While, cotton fabrics show opposite trends because of its higher moisture retention and insulation tendency (Ghali, Ghaddar, & Jones, 2002). And when Lurex is added. In Primary Sensory Properties the indices reflect that cotton sample have higher smoothness and total sensory scores allowing good tactile comfort and hand feel. However, PVT fabrics show lower smoothness and total sensory values and if Lurex is added it reduce comfortness with increase of Lurex yarn.

Pilling Property

The test results compare with ASTM D 3512 photographic standards random tumble pilling test method, it is noticeable that conventional cotton and PVT plain single jersey exhibited moderate pilling behavior

ASTM grade ≈ 2 & 3. This happens due to the loose lope structure and higher mobility, which allows fabric pills easily and as PVT has better pilling property than cotton.

Table 2. Pilling Property for Plain Single Jersey Sample

Yarn Type	Sl. No	Fabric Type	Average Point	ASTM Standard Meaning
Cotton	1.	Single Jersey	2	Moderate Pilling
	2.	Single Jersey with Lurex	5	No Pilling
	3.	Single Jersey Stripe with Lurex	3	Slight Pilling
PVT	4.	Single Jersey	3	Moderate Pilling
	5.	Single Jersey with Lurex	5	No Pilling
	6.	Single Jersey Stripe with Lurex	4	Moderate Pilling

However, when Lurex yarn adds to plain structure the test shows better outcome than no-integrated knitted fabric, where the performance of both cotton and PVT Lurex combining fabric has been improved maximum. The ASTM grade scale the result is 5 which means no pilling. For the third type of fabric (stripe with Lurex) cotton (ASTM grade ≈ 3.0) and PVT (ASTM grade ≈ 4) shows the same consequences of impact of lurx yarn as well as cotton and PVT (Smriti, & Islam, 2015).

Figure 3. Pilling Property of Single Jersey Fabric (with or without Lurex) at Variable Cotton & PVT Fiber%

Abrasion Test

The higher the weight loss in Martindale abrasion test the lower the abrasion resistance of fabric. It is clearly visible that cotton fabric has higher weight loss than pvt this is due to natural staple fiber structure.

Table 3. Abrasion Resistance of Plain Single Jersey Fabric

Yarn type	Sl.	Sample Name	Weight loss(gm)
Cotton	1.	Single Jersey	0.052
	2.	Single Jersey with Lurex	0.040
	3.	Single Jersey Stripe with Lurex	0.047
PVT	4.	Single Jersey	0.035

	5.	Single Jersey with Lurex	0.012
	6.	Single Jersey Stripe with Lurex	0.023

Figure 4. Abrasion Resistance of Single Jersey Fabric (with or without Lurex) at Variable Cotton & PVT Fiber%

In comparison to plain cotton single jersey fabrics exhibited slightly higher weight loss than plain cotton stripe with Lurex fabrics, while only Lurex resulted good abrasion property. Moreover, PVT fabrics showed greater abrasion resistance compared to cotton fabrics, both with and without Lurex. This behavior is likely due to the blended fiber composition (rayon, polyester, nylon), where differential fiber wear occurs under repeated abrasion.

Bursting Strength

Bursting strength test mainly measures the materials resistance to rupture and there is use of Lurex yarn so it definitely improves the resistance. The test results clearly demonstrate the superiority of PVT fabrics over cotton fabrics. It reveals a clear improvement in mechanical strength with the addition of Lurex yarn.

Table 4. Bursting Strength of Plain Single Jersey Fabric (Cotton & PVT)

SL	Name of the sample	Bursting Strength (Kpa)
1.	Cotton plain single jersey	689.4
2.	Cotton plain single jersey and Lurex	901.3
3.	Cotton plain single jersey Stripe with Lurex	728.7
4.	PVT plain single jersey	787.9
5.	PVT plain single jersey and Lurex	1000
6.	PVT plain single jersey Stripe with Lurex	1000

Figure 5. Bursting Strength (Kpa) of Single Jersey Fabric (with or without Lurex) at Variable Cotton & PVT Fiber%

For cotton the strength significant raise from 689.4 Kpa (plain single jersey) to 901.3 Kpa (Lurex blended). In contrary, PVT demonstrate better performance (maximum to 1000 Kpa) (Seval, 2021).

Shrinkage Test

Table 6. Shrinkage result of knitted fabric with or without Lurex (Cotton & PVT)

Yarn type	Sl.	Sample Name	Shrinkage%
Cotton	1.	Single Jersey	6
	2.	Single Jersey with Lurex	--
	3.	Single Jersey Stripe with Lurex	3
PVT	4.	Single Jersey	4
	5.	Single Jersey with Lurex	--
	6.	Single Jersey Stripe with Lurex	2

Figure 6. Shrinkage of Single Jersey Fabric (with or without Lurex) at Variable Cotton & PVT Fiber%

There are significant changes can analysis through this test. For plain single jersey the shrinkage percentages are high comparative to blended sample and there are no changes in Lurex mixed. However, for strip structure sample the percentage is minimal than plain ones. These trends occur because of the metallic yarn, which restricts loop movement and minimizes dimensional change. In between cotton and PVT fiber the result defers, natural fibers have more absorbency and high moisture vapor transport rate (MVTR) (Ramkumar, et al., 2007). In case of manmade fibers, they have less tendency. This is the main findings that PVT sample exhibited lower shrinkage.

Spirality

Table 7. Spirality Result of Knitted Fabric with or without Lurex (Cotton & PVT)

Yarn type	Sl.	Name of the sample	Spirality%
Cotton	1.	Single Jersey	5.05%
	2.	Single Jersey with Lurex	3.0%
	3.	Single Jersey Stripe with Lurex	3.57%
PVT	4.	Single Jersey	3.25%
	5.	Single Jersey with Lurex	1.15%
	6.	Single Jersey Stripe with Lurex	2.25%

Figure 7. Spirality of Single Jersey Fabric (with or without Lurex) at Variable Cotton & PVT Fiber%

Spirality is performed to measure dimensional stability parameter in apparels. From the test it is found that, there are a lot of revealing difference between natural and manmade fabric structure. The cotton plain single jersey exhibited a higher spirality value of approximately 5.05% while PVT single jersey fabric showed a lower spirality value of approximately 3.25%. this significant difference happens due to the natural twist liveliness of cotton yarn, higher moisture absorption, and unstable loop construction during weft knitting, which collectively increase skewness after washing. Contrary, presence of synthetic fibers in PVT, which have lower moisture absorption and better dimensional recovery compared to cotton. Furthermore, Lurex blended fabric in both categories show lower spirality percentage, this provides better dimensional stability control over fabric after washing.

Conclusion

This study indicates that integrating Lurex yarn into single jersey knitted fabrics provides a significant boost to their physical and mechanical performance, but it needs a careful balance with wearer comfort. By combining Lurex with both cotton and PVT yarns, the research shows that this metallic yarn does far more than just add a decorative shimmer; it fundamentally alters the fabric's structural integrity. The inclusion of Lurex effectively eliminates the common problem of pilling, elevating fabrics from a moderate pilling grade to a perfect rating. Furthermore, it improves the strength of the the knit fabric significantly.

From a structural angle, Lurex serves as a stabilizing agent. Its metallic properties restrict the movement of knit loops, which helps the fabric maintain its shape and lead to dimensionally stable. This leads to a marked reduction in both shrinkage and spirality after washing, particularly in cotton-based structures that are traditionally more prone to twisting and dimensional changes. While PVT blends naturally offer better stability, the addition of Lurex enhances this performance across all tested samples.

However, these mechanical gains come at the expense of certain comfort factors. While cotton remains the preferred choice for softness and breathability, the addition of Lurex reduces the overall smoothness and tactile comfort of the fabric. Because Lurex can increase skin sensitivity and decrease softness, it is most effectively used in garments designed for aesthetic appeal or for outer layers, such as winter sweaters, where visual impact and structural durability are prioritized over next-to-skin softness.

In brief, Lurex yarn is a versatile and valuable component for the modern textile industry, offering a unique combination of glamour and enhanced physical properties. As the field evolves toward sustainable manufacturing and the development of smart, conductive textiles, Lurex is well-positioned to remain a key material for designers looking to merge high-fashion aesthetics with superior performance.

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